

The Influence of Cortical Traveling Waves on the Reaction Speed of Subjects ^{*}

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Abstract. Cortical traveling waves have been extensively studied and are documented across various experimental animal models and humans using both direct and indirect recording methods. They have been implicated in fundamental processes including perception, memory, decision-making, consciousness, and sleep. While these waves are readily interpretable in microelectrode recordings, their detection in MEG or EEG data presents significant challenges due to the volume conduction properties of the brain. In noninvasive recordings, traveling waves manifest as phase differences in oscillatory activity across recording channels. Here, we employed an algorithm to compute instantaneous phase differences, leveraging a unique feature of the Vector View system’s planar gradiometers—specifically, their orthogonal orientation (rotated 90° relative to one another). This approach enabled us to detect rotating dipoles beneath the recording sensors, indicative of traveling waves within the underlying cerebral sulci. Our study demonstrated that during auditory presentation of individual words, increased wave detection time within specific cortical regions correlates with either acceleration or deceleration of behavioral responses during word recognition.

Keywords: cortical traveling waves, spontaneous neural activity, auditory presented, single words, behavioral response, MEG, phase difference, planar gradiometers

1 Introduction

Animal studies utilizing electrocorticography (ECoG), microelectrode technology, and optical imaging have demonstrated the existence of cortical traveling

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waves across micro-, meso-, and macroscales, spanning frequencies from infraslow to gamma rhythms [1–3]. These waves propagate both tangentially along the cortical surface and intralaminarly [1, 4]. While planar and radial wavefronts are most commonly described [5], spiral wave patterns are also observed [2]. Reflecting their broad physiological frequency range, wave velocities vary from millimeters to meters per second and depend critically on the propagation medium [3, 6]. Within intracortical networks, wave speeds align with action potential conduction along unmyelinated fibers (0.2 m/s) [7], whereas myelinated cortico-cortical connections support faster propagation (meters per second) [6].

Critically, volume conduction effects must be considered, as they can generate spurious fast-wave signatures. These arise from electric fields induced by rotating equivalent dipoles—a consequence of traveling wave propagation within cortical folds—particularly relevant in humans and higher mammals [5]. Such effects significantly impact noninvasive electroencephalography (EEG) and magnetoencephalography (MEG) recordings, manifesting as rotational field patterns and inter-channel phase differences in oscillatory activity [7, 8].

Rotating magnetic dipoles can be directly detected using pairs of planar gradiometers within a single sensor triplet—a design feature of MEG systems like VectorView. Our prior work demonstrated that mesoscopic traveling waves produce such rotational patterns in both EEG and MEG [9, 10]. Consequently, phase-difference analysis of MEG signals enables the detection of traveling waves when sensors overlie cerebral sulci.

Animal and computational studies indicate that traveling waves act as perceptual gates modulating behavior [11], including motor control processes [12]. Building on this evidence, our study investigates the influence of cortical traveling waves on behavioral response latency during auditory word recognition tasks.

2 Measurements

2.1 Subjects

The experiments involved 24 healthy subjects (17 women and 7 men) with normal hearing and an average age of 27.2 ± 4.6 years. All subjects were right-handed. They signed a voluntary consent form to participate in the experiment. The research protocol was approved by the ethics committee (see section 5). All studies were conducted between 9 a.m. and 4 p.m.

2.2 Stimuli

The subject listened to original words in the form of 8 Russian adjectives, related by semantic meaning and aligned by the duration of sound, which was 600, 700, 900 ms respectively for each of the 3 series. The original word was repeated 10 times in the series, i.e. each series of presentations contained 80 words. All words in the series were mixed in a pseudo-random order and two identical words never

followed each other. The sound pressure value was the same for each presentation and was about 60 dB. The frequency of the digitized words in the form of an audio file did not exceed 22 kHz. After the word was presented, the subject had to press the button of the hand-held manipulator if he understood the meaning of the presented word. The end of the word sound was followed by the next stimulus after 2000 ± 500 ms (randomized), but no later than 4000 ms after the previous presentation.

2.3 Experimental Procedure

Before the experiment, the coordinates of the anatomical reference points (the left and right preauricular points and the bridge of the nose) were determined using a FASTRAK three-dimensional digitizer (Polhemus, USA), as well as indicator inductance coils attached to the subject's scalp at the top of the forehead and behind the ears. During the experiment, the subject was in a magnetically shielded multilayer permalloy chamber (AK3b, Vacuumschmelze GmbH, Germany), and his head was placed in a fiberglass helmet, which was part of a fiberglass Dewar flask with a sensor matrix immersed in liquid helium. The subject sat in such a way that the surface of the head was as close as possible to the sensors. The sensors were superconducting loops in the form of 1 magnetometer and 2 gradiometers included in a single triplet. The recording magnetoencephalographic (MEG) installation "Neuromag Vector View" (Elekta Oy, Finland) had 102 triplets of SQUID sensors. To eliminate artifacts, sound stimuli were supplied through a pneumatic system that supplied sound from a standard audio stimulator. The stimulator was programmed using the Presentation software (USA, Neurobehavioral Systems, Inc). The subject was asked to relax and close his eyes. The right hand touched the remote control with buttons. After the series of presentations, the subject was given 1-2 minutes to rest.

3 Data Analysis

Distributions of subjects' reactions were constructed from the beginning of the word to the moment of pressing the remote control button. The normality of the reaction time distributions was analyzed for each subject and for the group using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Due to the fact that a violation of the normality of distributions was found in all subjects in at least one of the series of presentations, we removed outliers in the speed of the behavioral reaction to the beginning of the stimulus being listened to using the interquartile range (IQR) method. The duration (in ms) of detection of superficial local traveling waves in the grooves of the cerebral cortex was calculated using the method of assessing the phase delay of slow waves (alpha range).

The phase difference between two signals $v_1(t)$ and $v_2(t)$ obtained from MEG-sensors was estimated as follows (see e.g. [13] for more details). We compute the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of N signal samples. The DFT spectrum $X(\mathbf{k})$ can be found by the so-called Discrete-Time Fourier Transform (DTFT)

$X(e^{j\omega T})$ (j is the imaginary unit). This spectrum is continuous with respect to the frequency ω and has the period equal to ω_s .

The DTFT spectra of the signals $v_1(nT)$ and $v_2(nT)$ of the lengths NT have the form

$$\mathbf{V}_i(e^{j\omega T}) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} v_i(nT)e^{-j\omega_{sig}nT} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_i(nT)e^{-j\omega_{sig}nT} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2, \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of samples, ω_{sig} is the signal frequency, and T is the sampling interval. The two signals $v_1(nT)$ and $v_2(nT)$ are zero for $0 < n \leq N$.

Using the equality

$$e^{-j\omega_{sig}nT} = \cos(\omega_{sig}nT) - j \sin(\omega_{sig}nT), \quad (2)$$

we get

$$\mathbf{V}_i(e^{j\omega T}) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_i(nT) (\cos(\omega nT) - j \sin(\omega nT)). \quad (3)$$

As the DFT spectrum consists of the samples of the DTFT spectrum at the frequencies $\omega_k = k(\omega_s/N)$ (where ω_s is sampling frequency), we get

$$\mathbf{V}_i\left(\frac{k\omega_s}{N}\right) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_i(nT) \left(\cos\left(\frac{k\omega_s}{N}nT\right) - j \sin\left(\frac{k\omega_s}{N}nT\right) \right). \quad (4)$$

Finally, we find the phase of the two signals $v_i(nT)$ φ_i , $i = 1, 2$, as

$$\varphi_i = \arctan \frac{\text{Im}(\mathbf{V}_i(e^{-j\omega_i T}))}{\text{Re}(\mathbf{V}_i(e^{-j\omega_i T}))} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_1(nT) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{N}nk\right)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_1(nT) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{N}nk\right)} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2. \quad (5)$$

We calculate total traveling wave detection time (TWDT) using the relation

$$\text{TWDT} = \sum_{k=1}^{\omega_s(T-w)} \sum_{m=k}^{k+\omega_s w} \Phi_m(h), \quad (6)$$

$$\Phi_m(h) = \begin{cases} 0, & |\varphi_{1m} - \varphi_{2m}| \notin [\pi/2 - h, \pi/2 + h], \\ 1, & |\varphi_{1m} - \varphi_{2m}| \in [\pi/2 - h, \pi/2 + h] \end{cases},$$

where T is the length of the time interval (ms), w is the width of the sliding time window (ms), h is the phase tolerance (rad). The Pearson correlation between the reaction speed and the TWDT was calculated: a) the total interval (-250-1300 ms) for all channels for each subject; b) the total interval for each channel (triplet) for each subject; c) the pre-stimulus interval (-250-0 ms) for each channel (triplet) for each subject; d) the poststimulus interval(0-1250 ms) for each channel (triplet) for each subject; e) 5 poststimulus intervals (250 ms

each) for each channel (triplet) for each subject. The correlation values were selected at $p < 0.01$ for all subjects and the obtained data were summarized in a table. The tabular data were mapped and distributions were obtained in the triplet space for cases of positive, negative and mixed correlations. In the mixed case, when the correlation values overlapped, they were summed up.

4 Results

We analyzed the distribution of behavioral reaction times to word onsets among 24 subjects, yielding 240 total responses (3 sets per subject). The normality test (Shapiro-Wilk) revealed deviations from normal distributions in 45 of 72 sets (each subject demonstrated a non-normal distribution in at least 1 set). After removing outliers, group-level reaction times ranged from 14 ms to 2881 ms. Subject-level mean reaction times varied between 380 ms and 1635 ms, with standard deviations spanning 142 ms to 566 ms (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of behavioral response times (word-onset to keypress) across all trials and subjects ($N=24 \times 3$ series).

No significant correlation emerged between TWDT and response speed across all subjects, except in Series 2 (subject 22; see [16]). However, we identified significant ($p < 0.01$) positive (Fig. 2) and negative (Fig. 3) correlations between TWDT (interval: -250–1300 ms) and response speed at specific sensor triplets and series (Table 1). This analysis was extended to subintervals: pre-stimulus (-250–0 ms) and post-stimulus (0–1300 ms, 0–250 ms, 250–500 ms, 500–750 ms, 750–1000 ms, 1000–1250 ms; see [16]).

Significant correlations were found in all 24 subjects. In the general interval -250–1300 ms (Table 1), significant correlations were found in 90 triplets (3.75 per subject) in different series out of 306 possible, including 64 unique triplets

Fig. 2. Positive correlation example ($r = 0.44$, $p < 0.01$) between TWDT (Triplet 39; right parietal region) and response time (Subject 25, Series 1).

(2.7 per subject) out of 102 possible with a maximum correlation value of 0.47 and a minimum of -0.45. Positive correlations were found in 54 sensors, and a negative one was found in 36 in different series. The corresponding values for the prestimulus interval -250-0 ms were: 81 (3.38); 60 (2.50); 0.40/-0.45; 45; 36; for poststimulus 0-1300 ms: 97(4.2); 69 (3.0); 0.43/-0.48; 58; 39; for additional intervals 0-250 ms: 93 (3.9); 59 (2.5); 0.41/-0.40; 51; 42; 250-500 ms: 98 (4.3); 63 (2.7); 0.45/-0.40; 56; 42; 500-750 ms: 79 (3.4); 58 (2.5); 0.41/-0.43; 47; 32; 750-1000 ms: 83 (3.5); 60 (2.5); 0.40/-0.40; 54; 29; 1000-1250 ms : 86 (3.6); 60 (2.5); 0.48/-0.44; 52; 34.

The negative correlation magnitude varied in the range from -0.29 to -0.48, positive from 0.29 to 0.47. Negative correlations indicate faster with increased TWDT, positive correlations indicate slower responses with increased TWDT. Scalp topography maps of significant correlations (Fig. 4) were constructed using all valid triplet-subject data (group averaging was precluded by sparse per-subject data).

Topographic analysis revealed symmetrical negative (dominant on the left) and positive (dominant on the right) foci in the frontal areas of reliable correlation (Fig. 4). The left-sided negative focus, bilateral positive foci (right > left) in the central areas are visible on this map. An increase in negative correlations is noted in the left temporal region compared to the right hemisphere. The strongest positive focus is determined on the left and an adjacent negative focus in the occipital-parietal areas. In the inferior temporal region, a positive focus of correlation coefficients is noticeable on the left against the negative one on the right.

Fig. 3. Negative correlation example ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$) between total TWDT (Triplet 78; left occipital region) and response time (Subject 41, Series 1).

Fig. 4. Scalp distributions of negative (left), positive (center), and combined (right) correlation coefficients (thresholded at $p < 0.01$).

5 Discussion

This study provides novel evidence that cortical traveling waves, detected non-invasively via MEG phase-difference analysis, significantly modulate behavioral response speeds during auditory word processing. Our key finding—that the relationship between TWDT and reaction speed is region-specific, time-dependent, and bidirectional (facilitatory vs. inhibitory)—supports the hypothesis that traveling waves act as dynamic perceptual gates in humans [11], while extending

T	A	$r=$	$p=$	S	B	T	A	$r=$	$p=$	S	B	T	A	$r=$	$p=$	S	B
1	LT001	-0.34	0.0028	24	3	40	RP040	0.30	0.0087	25	3	75	LP075	0.31	0.0052	25	1
4	LT004	0.37	0.0007	23	2	40	RP040	0.30	0.0074	27	3	76	RP076	-0.30	0.0071	40	1
5	LT005	-0.32	0.0052	25	3	41	RP041	0.30	0.0062	25	1	78	LO078	0.42	0.0001	35	3
6	LT006	-0.33	0.0044	26	3	42	RP042	0.33	0.0035	24	2	78	LO078	-0.45	0.0001	41	1
7	LT007	-0.29	0.0097	27	3	42	RP042	0.33	0.0032	25	1	79	ZO079	0.37	0.0007	43	1
10	LF010	0.47	0.0000	25	3	43	RF043	0.37	0.0007	44	2	83	RP083	-0.33	0.0030	28	2
13	LP013	0.34	0.0021	40	1	44	RF044	-0.34	0.0025	46	3	83	RP083	0.29	0.0100	44	3
16	LP016	-0.37	0.0007	34	1	45	RF045	-0.30	0.0072	46	1	84	RT084	0.29	0.0095	24	2
16	LP016	0.30	0.0067	35	3	48	RT048	-0.29	0.0080	35	3	85	RP085	0.31	0.0046	27	2
16	LP016	0.30	0.0090	50	1	48	RT048	-0.34	0.0027	47	1	85	RP085	0.38	0.0006	40	1
17	LF017	-0.34	0.0025	47	2	49	RT049	-0.41	0.0002	22	2	86	RP086	-0.30	0.0084	35	1
17	LF017	0.35	0.0017	49	2	57	LT057	-0.32	0.0062	27	1	88	RO088	-0.29	0.0100	46	1
18	LF018	-0.40	0.0003	33	1	58	LT058	0.38	0.0004	42	3	88	RO088	0.37	0.0008	47	2
18	LF018	-0.32	0.0044	50	3	59	LT059	0.36	0.0012	33	1	89	RO089	0.33	0.0033	24	3
19	LF019	-0.32	0.0041	21	3	59	LT059	-0.41	0.0003	50	1	90	RO090	0.34	0.0034	25	2
19	LF019	0.33	0.0051	34	3	60	LT060	-0.30	0.0082	40	2	90	RO090	0.33	0.0028	34	1
22	MF022	0.31	0.0056	50	3	62	LO062	0.33	0.0033	24	2	93	RO093	0.34	0.0034	25	3
24	LF024	-0.32	0.0053	24	3	64	LO064	0.36	0.0011	42	3	94	RT094	-0.31	0.0057	44	3
25	LC025	-0.31	0.0047	35	2	65	LO065	-0.30	0.0094	33	3	95	RO095	0.30	0.0080	24	3
25	LC025	0.32	0.0042	46	3	65	LO065	0.30	0.0099	39	2	96	RO096	0.31	0.0087	27	1
27	RP027	0.31	0.0059	45	3	66	LO066	0.32	0.0051	26	2	96	RO096	0.41	0.0002	49	2
28	LP028	0.35	0.0028	27	1	67	LT067	0.33	0.0034	39	2	97	RO097	-0.33	0.0035	24	3
29	MF029	0.32	0.0035	42	2	68	LP068	0.32	0.0050	38	1	98	RO098	0.32	0.0054	38	1
31	RF031	-0.36	0.0009	34	1	69	LP069	0.30	0.0095	26	3	98	RO098	-0.31	0.0045	42	1
31	RF031	0.29	0.0091	45	3	72	LO072	0.32	0.0040	22	3	99	RT099	-0.34	0.0020	44	2
31	RF031	-0.31	0.0056	46	3	72	LO072	0.31	0.0064	28	1	100	RT100	-0.38	0.0006	45	3
32	RF032	-0.31	0.0061	41	2	72	LO072	0.29	0.0100	34	1	101	RT101	0.30	0.0078	42	3
36	RF036	0.33	0.0026	42	1	72	LO072	0.32	0.0034	49	3	101	RT101	0.34	0.0026	49	1
37	RF037	0.33	0.0029	34	2	74	LO074	-0.34	0.0020	25	1	102	RT102	-0.34	0.0020	46	3
39	RP039	0.44	0.0000	25	1	74	LO074	-0.31	0.0061	28	3	102	RT102	0.30	0.0076	48	3

Table 1. Significant correlations ($p < 0.01$) between TWDT (per triplet) and behaviour response time in the -250-1300 ms interval. T - Triplet ID; A - Anatomy (LF - left frontal, RF - right frontal, MF - midline frontal, LT - left temporal, RT - right temporal, LC - left central, RC - right central, LP - left parietal, RP - right parietal, LO - left occipital, RO - right occipital, MO - midline frontal, MO - midline occipital); r -correlation; p -significance; S - Subject ID; B - Series.

this framework in three critical ways. Traveling waves as spatiotemporal organizers of behavior the observed correlations between TWDT and response speed (Figs. 2–4, Table 1) align with animal studies demonstrating that wave propagation coordinates neuronal ensembles during sensory processing [1, 11, 12]. Notably, pre-stimulus effects (-250–0 ms) showed significant correlations in 58% of sensors, suggesting that spontaneous pre-activation states structured by traveling waves bias subsequent perceptual performance [11]. This echoes models

where prestimulus alpha/beta waves "prime" cortical excitability [5], though our data reveal a more complex spatiotemporal landscape. The bidirectionality of effects—where increased TWDT accelerated reactions in some regions (negative r) but slowed them in others (positive r)—implies that waves exert both facilitatory and inhibitory control. For example: Frontal/left-central foci (negative r) may reflect motor preparation [12], where waves synchronize action-planning networks. Right temporo-parietal foci (positive r) could gate attentional resources, with prolonged wave activity suppressing distractor processing [11]. Hemispheric asymmetry and functional specialization topographic maps (Fig. 4) revealed hemispheric dissociation: Left-dominant negative correlations (accelerated responses) clustered in perisylvian regions (fronto-temporal-central), aligning with left-hemisphere specialization for rapid phonological access [14]. Right-dominant positive correlations (slowed responses) localized to parietal-occipital regions, potentially reflecting top-down suppression of task-irrelevant visuospatial networks. The strongest positive focus at the left parietal-occipital junction (angular gyrus) is particularly interesting. This region integrates auditory-phonological with visuo-semantic information [15]; prolonged wave activity here may index deeper semantic processing, trading speed for accuracy. Our approach leveraged the orthogonal gradiometer configuration of VectorView sensors to detect sulcal wave propagation—a significant advance over volume-conduction-distorted EEG methods [5, 8]. The fact that up to 64% of triplets showed significant effects confirms the effectiveness of phase difference algorithms for tracking waves in the folded crust. However, the sparse effects that are specific to each subject (significant effects were found at 2.5 to 4.3 sensors on average per subject) highlight some problems: traveling waves may be transient phenomena (with the sensor being located over a gyrus), requiring trial-by-trial analysis rather than cross-subject averaging. Despite the existing problems, it can be concluded that cortical traveling waves are not epiphenomena but active organizers of human cognition. By propagating through specialized networks—facilitating processing in language-dominant regions while inhibiting task-irrelevant areas—they dynamically gate perceptual decisions. Our findings position TWDT as a novel biomarker for cortical communication efficiency, with implications for basic cognitive neuroscience and translational research.

6 Ethical Approval

The study was carried out in accordance with The Code of Ethics of the World Medical Association (Declaration of Helsinki) for experiments involving humans, and the Ethical committee of the Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of the RAS approved the research protocols (Protocol No. 5 of July 18, 2023).

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